

To eat or not to Eat: Modeling food waste behavior at a hotel breakfast buffet

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ABSTRACT

Food loss and waste are increasingly recognized as the outcomes of complex, interconnected social and environmental dynamics rather than isolated individual choices. In this study, we adopt a complex systems approach to explore how micro-level behaviors and interactions within commercial dining settings give rise to emergent patterns of food waste. We present an agent-based model that integrates a psychologically realistic representation of individual decision-making, grounded in the HUMAT socio-cognitive architecture. Here, artificial agents balance multiple motives — including social, experiential, and values-based drivers — while operating within a context shaped by the Motivation, Opportunities, and Abilities (MOA) framework from the social sciences. The simulated population represents diners in buffet-style environments. Individuals follow rules influenced by their motivations, opportunities, and abilities, which dictate factors such as the timing of their meal, portion sizes, frequency of servings, and amount of leftovers on their plates. Results highlight that the motives of conformism and sustainability have the strongest impact on food waste levels, with higher values drastically reducing leftovers. The model also shows that extra servings—particularly in scenarios with normal plate sizes—are strongly associated with increased waste. These findings underscore how behavioral drivers and situational constraints interact to shape food waste patterns, supporting the model's application in simulating context-sensitive interventions for promoting sustainable and responsible consumption.

1. Introduction

Food systems are highly complex and encompass multiple scales and processes, from agricultural practices to distribution activities and consumer behavior (Gamboa et al., 2016; Heller and Keoleian, 2003). They are shaped by a wide range of factors, including biological, economic, political, social, technological, and cultural influences (Tansey and Worsley, 2014; Ericksen, 2008). This complexity is also evident in the challenge of food waste, which accounts for approximately one third of total food production (UNEP, 2021). Addressing Food Loss and Waste (FLW) is therefore essential for building more sustainable food systems and promoting responsible consumption (Boiteau and Pingali, 2023). At the global level, this is reflected in the Sustainable Development Goals (SGD 12, target 12.3), aiming to reduce per capita food waste by half at the consumer level and reduce food losses along the production and supply chain by 2030 (United Nations).

FLW occurs across all stages of the food system, including

cultivation, harvest, post-harvest, distribution, retail, and consumption (Nicastro and Carillo, 2021), and its causes are highly context-dependent. In restaurants and similar establishments, consumer-level food waste presents a major challenge (Attiq et al., 2021). A significant amount of Food Waste (FW) in these settings results from customers' leftovers, and identifying strategies to change this behavior remains a difficult task (Filimonau et al., 2020). According to the Food Waste Index Report 2024, 28 % of global FW occurs within food service settings (i.e. restaurants, hotels, canteens) (UNEP–United Nation Environment Programme, 2024). It is further estimated that in 2023, the food service sector generated 12.9M tons of surplus food, of which above 80 % was ultimately wasted and sent to landfills or incineration (Astashkina et al., 2025).

FW represents both an economic burden for the hospitality sector and an environmental cost for society. Hotels and restaurants face direct losses from over-purchasing and preparation, alongside operational costs of waste disposal (Astashkina et al., 2025). In the UK alone, the

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hospitality sector produces FW valued at £2.5 billion annually (WRAP, 2013). Environmentally, FW contributes to resource depletion and greenhouse emissions, with estimates suggesting that 1 kg of FW generates the depletion of 2.9 tons of natural resources and around 2 kg of CO₂ equivalent emissions (BIO Intelligence Services, 2010). These impacts are amplified by methane released from landfilled FW (U.S. Environmental Protection Agency (EPA), 2023).

In the hospitality sector FW can occur during food preparation, serving, and consumption. Key drivers include the kitchen's ability to predict demand, the type of menu offered (e.g. à la carte, buffet-style), preparation methods, and the preference for fresh ingredients (McAdams et al., 2019). In the serving phase, larger plates have been associated with increased FW, as they can create consumption norms that encourage large portions (Wansink and van Ittersum, 2013; van Ittersum and Wansink, 2012).

Buffet-style service is particularly waste-intensive, as it allows customers to self-serve and choose both the type and quantity of food. This often leads to excessive portioning and higher levels of FW due to the combination of overproduction and individual over-serving (Juvan et al., 2017). Buffets require kitchens to prepare large quantities of food to maintain guest satisfaction, despite uncertainties in guest numbers and preferences. Further, the abundance and variety of food, the hedonic mindset of guests (especially while on vacation), and the desire to maximize value-for-money, all contribute to increased plate waste (Juvan et al., 2017). These factors make buffet-style service a recognized hotspot for FW in hotels and restaurants.

Despite the relevance of FW at both the industry and societal levels, research on effective strategies to reduce FW in food service settings, specifically within hospitality, remains limited. In relation to post-consumption waste (i.e., plate waste), several interventions have been tested to reduce FW in hospitality settings. These include reducing plate size (Kallbekken and Sælen, 2013), communication campaigns (Antonschmidt and Lund-Durlacher, 2021) (Cozzio et al., 2021), and gamified incentives (Dolnicar et al., 2020). While many show promising results, such as a 34 % reduction in plate waste through game-based strategies (Dolnicar et al., 2020), they often target isolated factors and lack consideration of the broader behavioral context. Moreover, discrepancies between stated intentions and actual behavior, as seen in studies combining quasi-experiments with surveys (Juvan et al., 2025), highlight the influence of situational and social dynamics. As such, these interventions provide only a partial understanding of the behavioral drivers of food waste.

In reality, the decision to waste food arises from a complex interplay of individual and socio-behavioral drives (Alsuwaidi et al., 2022) including personal motives (e.g., indulgence), situational factors (e.g., time constraints), social norms, etc. This fragmented understanding limits our ability to fully grasp the drivers of FW in buffet settings and hinders the development of effective, targeted interventions.

Given the multitude of interrelated factors influencing food waste—ranging from individual motives and situational cues to social and structural dynamics, FW in buffet settings must be understood as a complex system. Addressing this issue effectively requires analytical approaches capable of capturing the non-linear interactions, feedback loops, and emergent patterns that characterize such systems. In recent years, a few complex-oriented approaches have applied to study FLW, including systems and design thinking (Lake et al., 2020), conceptual frameworks based on complexity theory (Alsuwaidi et al., 2022; Papargyropoulou et al., 2016), network analysis (Ghinoi et al., 2020; Xu et al., 2016), and agent-based models (ABMs) (Ravandi and Jovanovic, 2019).

Agent-based modeling (ABM) offers a promising solution to this challenge. ABMs simulate individual agents with diverse characteristics and decision-making processes, embedded in dynamic social and physical environments (Jager and Edmonds, 2015). This makes them particularly well-suited for modeling complex systems like food waste at buffets, where behavior emerges from interactions among individual,

social and contextual factors. By enabling bottom-up exploration of these processes, ABMs help uncover how micro-level mechanisms give rise to macro-level patterns—such as aggregate waste levels or responses to contextual changes. ABMs can therefore deepen our understanding of the behavioral and systemic drivers of FW in buffet contexts, identify leverage points within the system, and allow virtual evaluation of potential interventions and policy measures in a virtual setting before real-world implementations (Jager and Edmonds, 2015).

This study aims to explain how FW behaviors can plausibly emerge from the interplay of individual, contextual, and social mechanisms using an ABM of a hotel “all-you-can-eat” breakfast buffet. We began by identifying the main behavioural and contextual elements related to FW, integrating them into a theoretical framework, and subsequently conceptualizing the model. Three key processes were identified as influencing individual decision-making: motivations, opportunities and abilities, and social norms. To represent how individuals make choices based on their motivations, we applied the HUMAT framework (Wander et al., 2025). To account for the influence of opportunities and abilities, we incorporated the motivation, opportunities, and abilities (MOA) framework. Finally, to grasp the connection between social norms and FW-related behaviors, we operationalized the definition of social norms and conceptualized how individuals' decisions and actions are shaped by these norms (Vittuari et al., 2023). These theories and frameworks were formalized into an integrated, agent-based framework. Following Epstein's argument for generative explanation (Epstein, 2008), we use the model to show how macro-level patterns, such as plate waste, can arise from the interaction of heterogeneous agents operating under well-founded behavioral rules. Our goal is to establish the feasibility and plausibility of these mechanisms, assess their internal coherence, and show that the model can reproduce empirically grounded patterns of food waste. This provides a critical foundation for using the model in future research to test targeted intervention strategies and explore their systemic effects. At this stage, however, we focus on model explanation and validation, ensuring that the mechanisms are both theoretically sound and computationally capable of generating behavior that resembles reality.

2. Methods

The model described in this section was developed as part of the EU HORIZON CHORIZO project (<https://chorizoproject.eu/>), which is dedicated to advancing our understanding of how social norms influence behaviors associated with generating food waste. A key objective of the project is to develop computer simulations that can assess the effectiveness of interventions aimed at reducing food loss and waste. The agent-based model presented here builds directly upon insights from the CHORIZO Project (Deliverable 3.1) (Vittuari et al., 2023), which establishes a theoretical foundation that unifies the MOA and HUMAT frameworks (described below).

2.1. Variable selection process

The variables included in the model were derived through a theory-informed review of empirical research on food waste and consumption behavior, especially in buffet and hospitality contexts. We used the HUMAT socio-cognitive architecture and the MOA framework to organize and justify the inclusion of motives, opportunities, and abilities. Motives such as hunger, fullness, indulgence, conformism, weight control, and sustainability were derived from empirical studies or inferred from documented behavioral patterns (e.g. (Zhu and Liu, 2024), and (Cialdini et al., 1991)). Contextual variables such as plate size, food diversity, available time, and self-control were incorporated to capture how environmental and individual constraints modulate decision-making. Empirical estimates of portion sizes were informed by observed data from hotel settings and existing nutrition studies (Zheng et al., 2016; Collins et al., 2015).

2.2. The HUMAT model

The HUMAT model integrates theoretical concepts related to human motives, cognitive dissonance, and individual and social decision-making strategies within social contexts like networked communities. This model facilitates the simulation of decision-making scenarios where individuals must choose between two or more choices, such as deciding how much food to serve themselves or whether to finish their meal. In HUMAT, each agent is characterized by a set of motives influencing their decisions, categorized into three types.

1. **Experiential Motives:** Factors such as hunger or fullness;
2. **Social Motives:** The need for social belonging, leading to conformity with norm-driven behaviors;
3. **Value Motives:** Principles such as sustainability values.

Motives guide the decision-making process, with each motive assigned an importance value representing its relevance to the agent. Further, agents hold beliefs about how available choices satisfy each of these motives. When faced with a decision, agents evaluate how each choice satisfies their motives, with satisfaction levels ranging from dissatisfying to satisfying $[-1,1]$, respectively). Because each motive has its own choice-specific satisfaction, different choices can satisfy the same motive differently. For instance, choosing a vegetarian meal may be dissatisfying for someone accustomed to eating meat (an experiential motive) but satisfying if they care about animal welfare (a value motive).

In our simulation, choice-specific satisfactions for experiential and value motives remain constant over time, while those for social motives are dynamic. Social motive satisfactions change according to the proportion of individuals in the agent’s social network who select a given choice. Specifically, the satisfaction of a social motive is directly proportional to the percentage of network members choosing that choice, weighted by the importance the individual assigns to conformity.

We defined the network of agents influencing the focal agent’s behavior as those having served themselves breakfast (or finished their meals) in the minutes prior to the focal agent serving itself breakfast (or finishing its meal). This time-based definition implicitly includes companions or acquaintances, as they would typically take food at similar times and thus fall within the same network. For simplicity, however, their influence is treated in the same way as that of other individuals present.

2.2.1. Making a choice

At the start of the simulation, the initial satisfaction levels for experiential and value motives are randomly determined using a normal distribution with defined mean (M) and standard deviation (SD). The satisfaction for social motives is calculated based on the proportion of agents in the ego’s network selecting a particular choice. The formula used for this calculation normalizes the satisfaction value in the continuum $[-1, 1]$, Equation (1).

$$S_{c,m_i} = PA_{c_i} * 2 - 1, \tag{1}$$

where S_{c,m_i} is the satisfaction of choice c for social motive m , for agent i , at time step t , and PA_{c_i} is the proportion of alters selecting choice c , at time step t .

When making a choice, agents calculate the total satisfaction (TS) they derive from each choice by evaluating how well it meets their different motives’ satisfactions, equation (2).

$$TS_{c_i} = \frac{\sum_{m=1}^N S_{c,m_i} * I_{m_i}}{N}, \tag{2}$$

where TS_{c_i} is the total satisfaction of choice c , for agent i , at time step t , S_{c,m_i} is the satisfaction of choice c for social motive m , for agent i , at time step t , I_{m_i} is the importance of motive m , for agent i , N is the total number

of motives.

Agents then select the choice with the highest total satisfaction score. If after making a choice, the difference between the highest and second-highest TS is lower than 10 %, the agent reevaluates its choice based on the dissonance status. Dissonance status is a measure of how balanced the agent’s TS s are.

To calculate dissonance status, for each choice c we calculate the motive impact score (MIS) of every motive m as in equation (3):

$$MIS_{c,m_i} = S_{c,m_i} * I_{m_i}, \tag{3}$$

Where notation is the same as in equation (2).

MIS scores are compiled in an evaluation list, $E_c = \{ MIS_1, MIS_2, MIS_3, \dots, MIS_m \}$, and categorized into positive (satisfying) and negative (dissatisfying) groups, reflecting non-conflicting scores. The absolute values of these scores are then summed separately. The sum of the positive and negative scores are denoted as S_{sum} and D_{sum} , respectively. The dissonant and consonant values for choice c , of agent i , at time step t , are then:

$$Dissonant_{c_i} = \min(S_{sum}, D_{sum}), \tag{4}$$

$$Consonant_{c_i} = \max(S_{sum}, D_{sum}), \tag{5}$$

The dissonant value represents the smaller total of non-conflicting MIS s, and the consonant one the larger total of non-conflicting MIS s. The dissonance status of choice c , of agent i , at time step t , is then calculated as:

$$Dissonancestatus_{c_i} = \frac{Dissonant_{c_i}}{Consonant_{c_i} + Dissonant_{c_i}}, \tag{6}$$

and it represents how balanced the conflicting MIS s are. A value close to one indicates high dissonance (balanced conflict), that is, the agent is quite torn apart about choice c because of a similar magnitude of positive and negative MIS s. A value close to 0 indicates low dissonance (unbalanced conflict), that is, the agent is not conflicted by its choice because either all or most MIS s are negative or positive.

The agent selects the choice with the lowest dissonance status, provided the difference between the lowest and second-lowest dissonance statuses is less than 10 %. Otherwise, the agent reassesses its decision-making process based solely on experiential motives and selects the choice with the highest TS (2). If the difference between the highest and second-highest TS is still less than 10 %, the agent selects randomly between the two choices with the highest TS .

We adapted the original HUMAT model (Wander et al., 2025), so here there are no agent-specific social networks, that is, agents do not inquire or signal others in their social network when they feel conflicted with preferred choice. For more detailed information on the HUMAT model see Wander et al. (2025).

2.3. The MOA framework

The MOA framework was first proposed by MacInnis et al. (MacInnis et al., 1991) and further developed and applied to food waste (FW) within the EU Refresh project to systematically analyze drivers of FLW behavior. According to this framework, consumers’ information processing and consequent decisions are mediated by personal motivations, opportunities, and abilities. FLW behaviors are driven not only by personal factors but also by the context within which consumers find themselves, interpreting FLW food waste as an unintended consequence of iterative decisions and behaviours driven both by internal (individual) and external (social and societal) factors (Quested et al., 2013; Setti et al., 2018; Vittuari et al., 2023).

Motivations represent the intentions to carry out a set of actions and can influence FLW behaviors by affecting the individuals’ attitudes, perceptions of control, capabilities, and effectiveness in minimizing FLW. Factors such as awareness, consciousness of global impacts,

emotions, and engagement also drive motivations to minimize FLW. Furthermore, some motivations are represented by social norms since behaviors are influenced by what others do (descriptive social norms) and by what others' expect (injunctive social norms). For our modeling purposes, we identified six motives relevant to FLW decisions in a breakfast buffet context: hunger, fullness, conformism, indulgence, desire to control weight, and sustainability (see below).

Ability encompasses individuals' capacities to manage and reduce FW through personal knowledge and skills, including planning, organizational abilities, purchasing skills, food preparation expertise, and knowledge of proper storage and food safety assessment (Vittuari et al., 2021). For our modeling purposes, two abilities were relevant: the ability to self-control (in relation to the motives of indulgence and the desire to control weight) and the ability to choose preferred food (in relation to food diversity) - see below.

Opportunity refers to individuals' ability to access external resources, both tangible and intangible, such as time, technology, and infrastructure. This encompasses physical access to food production, distribution, and consumption, as well as access to food services, including tools for storing and cooking. Intangible resources may include the availability of time for food-related activities and the habits involved in managing cooking and storing tasks (Vittuari et al., 2021). In our model, individuals are presented with time available as an opportunity to serve themselves food and complete their meal; plate size serves as both an opportunity and a constraint, for the amount of food they can serve themselves; and food diversity as an opportunity to choose what they prefer (see below).

2.4. Social norms

Social norms are rules and expectations about behavior that are socially enforced (CHORIZO Project Consortium, 2024a; Vittuari et al., 2023), influencing attitudes, beliefs, and actions. In the context of FW in buffet settings, empirical studies suggest that they play an important role in regulating food consumption, preservation, and disposal. Following Cialdini et al.'s Focus theory of Normative Conduct (Cialdini et al., 1991), and more recent developments in norm theory (Gelfand et al., 2024), we distinguish between two types of social norms: (a) injunctive norms, which refer to perceptions of what behaviors *ought* to be performed because they are socially approved or disapproved by a specific reference group, and (b) descriptive norms, which refer to perceptions of what behaviors *are* commonly done in a given situation or context. Descriptive norms thus prompt individuals to conform because the common behavior is perceived as effective rather than expected, while injunctive norms involve the reinforcement of expected behaviors through rewards or punishments.

In our model, we map this distinction explicitly: injunctive and descriptive social norms are operationalized as two different motives: desire to control weight and conformism. The desire to control weight operates as an injunctive norm, as it reflects internalization of perceived societal approval or disapproval of body image and is often reinforced through social feedback such as praise, acceptance, criticism, or social exclusion. Conformism, on the other hand, is a descriptive norm, it captures the tendency of agents to align their portion sizes and likelihood of finishing food with the behavior of others in their immediate reference group (i.e., those who have recently served themselves or finished eating). This aligns with descriptive norm theory because behavior is adopted through observation of what is prevalent rather than through explicit instruction.

2.5. Integration of HUMAT, MOA, and social norms

The HUMAT, MOA, and social norms frameworks offer complementary perspectives on the drivers of behavior, but their integration into a single modeling approach involves reconciling important conceptual and operational differences (Vittuari et al., 2023). At a high

level, both frameworks share a modular understanding of human behavior assuming that discrete motivational, contextual, and social forces can be identified and modeled, but differ in how these forces interact during decision-making.

The MOA framework provides a structural lens for categorizing the primary influences on behavior: Motivation, Opportunity, and Ability. It offers a static "snapshot" of the decision environment, identifying the factors necessary for behaviour to occur. However, MOA does not specify how multiple motivations interact or how they are internally evaluated or resolved when they conflict. Nor does offer a process model for dynamic decision-making over time.

HUMAT, by contrast, is a dynamic socio-cognitive architecture that models how agents integrate multiple motives, assess their relative importance, experience internal conflicts (e.g., cognitive dissonance), and—depending on the context—adjust their decisions through mechanisms such as social influence. HUMAT therefore provides a psychologically plausible account of how behavioral choices emerge from motive trade-offs.

Ontologically, the two frameworks are compatible: both assume that behavior arises from internal motives. Their integration allows us to enrich a high-level behavioral taxonomy (MOA) with a cognitively grounded mechanism (HUMAT). In practical terms, motivational states in MOA (e.g., the motivation to avoid food waste) are directly mapped onto HUMAT's three motive types—experiential, social, and value-based. For example, an agent's motivation to avoid food waste may reflect value motives (e.g., sustainability), experiential motives (e.g., hunger), or social motives (e.g., fear of judgment). HUMAT then operationalizes how these motives are weighted, prioritized, and acted upon.

Importantly, HUMAT on its own does not explicitly account for contextual constraints such as opportunity and ability. Here, MOA complements HUMAT by modeling how structural conditions (e.g., time constraints, plate sizes, food availability) affect the expression or suppression of motives. In our implementation, opportunities and abilities influence either the importance weights of motives or the satisfactions agents derive from them.

Social norms are embedded in both frameworks, but HUMAT enables a more granular treatment by distinguishing norms as either social motives (reflecting external pressures) or value motives (reflecting internalized beliefs). This dual representation aligns with the common distinction between descriptive and injunctive norms and allows us to simulate both conformity and norm internalization.

A more extensive theoretical discussion of this integration—particularly the behavioral logic linking opportunities and abilities to motive satisfaction—is available in CHORIZO Deliverable 3.1 (Vittuari et al., 2023).

This conceptual alignment provides a foundation for integrating MOA into HUMAT within the specific context of our model. The next step involves translating this conceptual mapping into concrete mechanisms. Motivations from MOA map directly onto HUMAT motives; meanwhile, opportunities and abilities act not as standalone drivers but as modulators that influence how motives are expressed in behavior. This is operationalized in our model as follows.

- **Available Time (Opportunity):** Limits the amount of time agents have to eat, which can lead to food waste if meals are not finished in time. Additionally, time availability can influence portion size decisions, but only for agents with high self-control. In this way, time available may indirectly affect how motives like hunger or indulgence are expressed behaviorally.
- **Plate Size (Opportunity):** Plate size modifies portion size decisions in the final stage. While it does not directly constrain specific motives, it restricts the portion options available to the agent, which may reduce the behavioral expression of motives that would otherwise result in larger portions.
- **Food Diversity (Opportunity):** Interacts with choosing ability and affects the likelihood that an agent can choose preferred food. For

instance, low diversity increases the probability of selecting non-preferred food, no matter the agent choosing ability. This indirectly reflects food attributes like taste and appearance, which influence whether food is eaten or wasted.

- **Choosing Ability (Ability):** Choosing ability affects the likelihood that an agent selects food it prefers. It plays a role in the decision about how much food is likely to be eaten or wasted.
- **Self-Control (Ability):** Self-control adjusts the decision on portion size in relation to the agent’s motivation to indulge and/or control weight. It directly modulates the expression of these two motives by increasing or decreasing the likelihood that the agent acts on them.

In summary, opportunities and abilities in our model do not function as independent drivers of behavior; rather, they act as modulators that shape how underlying motives are expressed in specific contexts. Opportunities represent structural or situational features that can amplify or constrain the influence of motives (e.g., plate size limiting the expression of indulgence). Abilities reflect personal capacities that condition how effectively an agent can act on a motive (e.g., self-control dampening the expression of indulgence or enhancing weight-control motives). This integrated approach enables the model to retain MOA’s clarity in structuring external contextual influences while leveraging HUMAT’s dynamic, motive-based decision-making process and the explicit injunctive-descriptive norm distinction to simulate how macro-level patterns of food waste emerge in buffet settings.

2.6. Overview of the model

This simulation examines food consumption in a social context, specifically a breakfast buffet. It considers motives, abilities, opportunities, and social norms as well as various social roles such as client, guest, in-group members (e.g., business guest) and gender roles. These behavioral drivers are consistent with factors suggested in previous empirical research on buffet consumption. Zhu and Liu (2024), for instance, discuss how people tend to overestimate how much they can eat in buffet settings, a tendency likely driven by hunger and indulgence, and emphasize the influence of social norms and weight-related concerns, which map onto conformism and the desire to control weight, respectively. Further, although not explicitly treated as a factor in their framework, sustainability features as a desirable behavioral outcome, justifying its inclusion here as a value-based motive. Moreover, mechanisms such as self-control, food diversity, choosing ability, plate size, and time availability plausibly shape how these drivers are expressed, by constraining or enabling agents’ ability to act in line with their preferences and thus are also included in the model as mechanisms that shape the feasibility and expression of agents’ decision-making.

Agents in the model make two main decisions: determining their portion size and deciding whether to finish or leave their food. Portion size decisions are influenced by five motives: hunger, fullness, indulgence, conformism, and the desire to control weight. Where conformism and the desire to control weight represent a descriptive and injunctive social norm, respectively. Additionally, external opportunities like available time and plate size, as well as individual abilities like self-control, also impact this decision. The decision to finish or leave food is influenced by opportunities such as food diversity and time available; the ability to choose a preferred food; and four motives: hunger, fullness, conformism, and sustainability values. The subsequent sections provide a brief model description and detailed descriptions of the causal relationships within each of the decision-making processes.

2.6.1. Brief model description

The model, implemented in AnyLogic v8.7.10 and available at <https://gitlab.norceresearch.no/cmss/chorizo>, simulates the dining behavior of individuals in a hotel with access to a breakfast buffet.

The population within the model represents guests, and each guest is depicted as an agent characterized by two attributes: gender (male/

female) and guest type (business, non-business). The behavior of individual guests is governed by specific rules that determine: (a) the time they choose to go for their meal, (b) the portion size of food they serve themselves on their plates, (c) the number of times they serve themselves food during the meal and (d) the amount of food left uneaten on their plates (see Fig. 1).

The hotel buffet operates daily for a fixed duration of 3 h, representing typical breakfast hours (e.g., 7–10 a.m.). Guests can enter the

Fig. 1. Flow diagram of the model.

buffet 5 min after opening and can serve themselves until 5 min before closing time. Food is available *ad libitum* without restrictions, and guests decide on the portion size of food they serve themselves (small, normal, large) or choose not to consume any food. Food diversity is represented as a continuum variable ranging from 0 (lowest diversity) to 1 (highest diversity).

The model runs for one day and each agent makes decisions in the following order: (1) mealtime, (2) portion size of food, (3) duration of time spent eating, (4) amount of food left on their plates, (5) subsequent servings during the meal. If an agent chooses a subsequent serving, decisions 2–5 are repeated until the agent decides not to serve itself more food.

Business guests determine their mealtime by sampling from a triangular distribution with parameters (min = 5, max = 115, mode = 30 min), reflecting an average mealtime of 7:30 a.m., with the earliest and latest times being 7:05 a.m. and 8:55 a.m., respectively. Non-business guests set their mealtime using a similar triangular distribution (min = 5, max = 175, mode = 90 min), indicating an average mealtime of 8:30 a.m., with the earliest and latest times being 7:05 a.m. and 9:55 a.m., respectively.

2.6.2. Portion size decision

When serving food, agents decide whether to opt for nothing (0), a small (S, approx. 200 g), normal (N, approx. 300 g), or large (L, approx. 400 g) food portion. These values reflect typical combined meal portions and were informed by empirical studies on real-world food serving behavior (Zheng et al., 2016; Collins et al., 2015; Fay et al., 2015). This process involves four decision stages, considering various motives, abilities, and opportunities (Fig. 2). In stage 1, agents determine the portion size based on five motives: hunger, fullness, desire to control weight, desire to indulge oneself and conformism. In stage 2, the previously decided portion size is adjusted based on time availability (opportunity) and self-control (ability). In stage 3, agents may further modify their decision about the portion size at the very moment of serving themselves food based on their self-control and degree of indulgence and motivation to being thin. Finally, in stage 4 agents modify their portion size based on the plate size offered by the hotel (opportunity). The stages for portion size decision are described in detail in the Supplementary Material.

2.6.3. Time required for eating the served portion

The time needed to eat depends on the portion size served. Small portions require an average of 10 min ($M = 10$ min, $SD = 1$ min), normal 15 min ($M = 15$ min, $SD = 1$ min), and large ones 20 min ($M = 20$ min, $SD = 1$ min).

2.6.4. Finishing or leaving food on plate decision

The amount of uneaten food left by the agent on the plate depends on specific abilities, opportunities, and motivations and occur on the stages depicted in Fig. 3. The stages for finishing or leaving food are described in detail in the Supplementary Material.

3. Analytical quality assurance

Having described the structure and behavioral mechanisms of the model, we next assess its performance through a suite of complementary analytical quality assurance steps designed to ensure internal coherence, robustness, and alignment with real-world patterns. These steps provide multiple perspectives on model quality. Model verification, based on extreme parameter scenarios, confirms the internal logic and structural validity of the model. Consistency analysis establishes the minimum number of replications needed to reduce stochastic uncertainty. Local sensitivity analysis examines the model’s response to variation in individual parameters under controlled conditions, while global sensitivity analysis explores the combined effects of varying all parameters simultaneously, identifying main effects, interactions, and nonlinearities. Together, these analyses provide a rigorous foundation for interpreting results and increase confidence in the model’s ability to generate plausible, empirically grounded patterns of food waste behavior.

3.1. Collection of simulation data

For each simulation run, we collected the average amount of left-overs in grams per agent. Leftovers were generated from two sources: non-preferred food (when agents selected undesired food) and preferred food (when agents chose not to finish their meal) (see decision stages in Fig. 3). We categorized the leftovers into three types: those from non-preferred food, preferred food, and the total amount (preferred and non-preferred).

Fig. 2. Decision process for selecting portion size. L-IND stands for low indulgence, H-IND for high indulgence, L-DBT for low desire to be thin and H-DBT for high desire to be thin.

Fig. 3. Decision process for finishing or leaving food on plate.

3.2. Model verification

To verify that the model behaved as expected and to check its internal logic, we ran seventeen scenarios in which one to three parameters related to motives, abilities, or opportunities were set to extreme values, while the remaining parameters were fixed at either zero or their default values. Thirteen scenarios confirmed that agents’ decisions on portion sizes and finishing or leaving food aligned with the predicted influence of their motives’ importances and abilities, while the other four scenarios confirmed that the amount of leftovers was consistent with agents’ high level of hunger, choosing ability, and food diversity. For a detailed description of the scenarios, parameter values, and results see Supplementary Material.

3.3. Consistency analysis

The Vargha-Delaney A-test was conducted to determine the necessary number of replications to reduce uncertainty in the results stemming from the model’s stochastic nature, and to assess the minimal sample size to ensure result convergence (Alden et al., 2014; Vargha and Delaney, 2000). This non-parametric test measures the effect size between two distributions by calculating a statistic ranging between 0 and 1. A score of 0.5 indicates similar medians, suggesting consistent results across replications. Values closer to 0.44 or 0.56 imply small differences; around 0.36 or 0.64 indicate moderate effects, and below 0.29 or above 0.71 represent large differences.

For this analysis, we used the amount of leftovers per person as the model output. The number of replications generated was 50, 100, 150, and 200 replications. We used twenty sets of each as input for the Vargha-Delaney A Test.

Results showed that the effect is small for about 100–150 model runs (values around 0.56 (Vargha and Delaney, 2000)), suggesting that the results stem from simulation-based experimentation rather than stochastic noise (see Supplementary Fig. 30). Based on this, we used 150 replications per parameter set in the local sensitivity analysis.

3.4. Local sensitivity analysis

Local sensitivity analysis examines how variation in a single parameter affects model outputs while keeping all other parameters constant. This allows us to identify which parameters the model is most sensitive to. In our case, the analysis focused on agents’ motives (hunger, fullness, indulgence, desire to be thin, sustainability, and conformism) and self-control.

To determine the values of the parameters to keep constant, we performed a preliminary calibration experiment using AnyLogic’s optimization engine. AnyLogic’s optimization engine automatically

searches within the specified parameter ranges to find the combination of values that best meets a defined objective. In our case, minimizing the difference between simulated and observed average leftovers per guest (see section 4.1, Empirical data). The values obtained from the optimization experiments are shown in Table 1. The number of agents used in the optimization was 100 hotel guests, and the parameters’ value ranges were between 0 and 1.

After calibrating the model to match the observed left overs per guest, we systematically varied each motive —fullness, hunger, indulgence, weight control, conformism, sustainability— and self-control individually from 0 to 1 in 0.1 increments, while holding all other parameters constant (Table 1). Each condition was simulated 150 times, and the amount of leftovers was recorded as the primary output for analysis. To assess the model’s sensitivity to each parameter, we performed an ANOVA test ($\alpha = 0.01$) on this output.

The local sensitivity analysis identified conformism and sustainability as the primary motives influencing the amount of leftovers generated. Here, we present these results, while the findings for all motives and self-control are provided in the supplementary material.

Figs. 4 and 5 show the effect of conformism and sustainability on the amount of leftovers generated, respectively. In both cases, the ANOVA results ($\alpha = 0.01$) indicated a significant difference between the parameter values (0.01–1) for the motives and self-control.

We used results of the local sensitivity analysis to further guide the selection of parameter values and model calibration. This was necessary since some of the parameter values in the initial calibration were unrealistic (e.g., average values of fullness and hunger, see Table 1).

4. Empirical validation

4.1. Empirical data

In a different study, empirical data from eight hotels in Norway were

Table 1
Parameters obtained from the optimization.

Parameter	Value
Average desire to control weight	0.400
Average conformism	0.200
Average fullness	0.500
Average hunger	0.236
Average indulgence	0.697
Average sustainability	0.350
Business proportion	0.300
Choosing ability	0.300
Food diversity	0.363
Left-over percentage	0.100
Self-control	0.446

Fig. 4. Average value of leftovers (grams per person) over 150 runs, for each value of average conformism.

Fig. 5. Average value of leftovers (grams per person) over 150 runs, for each value of average sustainability.

collected by Strawberry Hotels and kindly shared with us for research purposes. This data includes daily information on the number of business and non-business guests and the amount of food waste from buffet breakfasts. The data was gathered as part of an experiment designed to understand how messages displayed at the buffet, aimed at raising awareness about food waste, affected the amount of food left over each day. Detailed information regarding the data and collection procedures is available in Deliverable 2.3 from the CHORIZO Project (CHORIZO Project Consortium, 2024a).

The experiment ran from March to September 2023 during which hotels displayed different messages according to the treatment. Each hotel received three treatments over time: a control treatment, where no messages were displayed; a positive message treatment; and a provocative message treatment. The hotels recorded the total amount of food waste (leftovers) and the number of guests at the buffet.

4.2. Model calibration and validation

To calibrate our model, we used the data collected under the control treatment and the amount of food wasted per guest per day. After excluding missing data, the final dataset comprised 493 days in total, aggregated across all the hotels. Using AnyLogic's optimization engine,

we identified the combination of parameter values that either maximize or minimize a specific model output. In our case, the target output was the amount of leftovers per person per day, which is approximately 28 g based on experimental data (Table 3). The optimization process determined the parameter configuration that reproduces this observed value.

We first fixed values of conformism and sustainability at 0.175 and 0.25. We did so because the local sensitivity analysis showed that these values produced a reasonable variation in the amount of leftovers generated per person. Lower values led to significantly higher leftovers, while higher values reduced leftovers to zero (Figs. 4 and 5).

Second, we adjusted the average values for hunger and fullness, setting hunger to 0.7 and fullness to 0.3. While the sensitivity analysis suggested that values between 0.1 and 0.4 for fullness aligned well with the experimental data (see Supplementary Material), the optimal values for hunger were unexpectedly close to zero. In the initial optimization experiments, these values were reversed, fullness exceeded hunger (Table 1) which was unrealistic, given that agents represent individuals arriving at a breakfast buffet in the early morning, likely without having eaten. Correcting this inconsistency ensured the parameters better reflected real-world conditions.

Third, the average desire to control weight was set to 0.4, based on the local sensitivity analysis results indicating that values between 0.1 and 0.5 aligned well with the experimental data (see Supplementary Material). This value represents a moderate level of concern with weight control, consistent with a population where individuals generally care about appearance and health, but are not excessively focused on it.

Finally, the remaining four parameters —average indulgence, choosing ability, food diversity, and self-control (each ranging from 0 to 1)— were recalibrated using AnyLogic's optimization engine. We allowed these parameters to range between 0 and 1 since the results from the local sensitivity analysis provided a wide range of possible values. To guide the optimization experiments, we used again the experimental data to guide the optimum output (close to 28 g of food per guest per day). Table 2 shows the set of parameters found during this second optimization experiment. Using these values, we then ran the model for the same number of days of the empirical data (493 days).

Descriptive statistical analysis of the hotel data showed an average of 27.94 g of food waste per guest per day, with a standard deviation of 15.41 g (Table 3). The model simulation, run over the same number of days, produced an average of 30.20 g of leftovers per guest per day, with a standard deviation of 14.68 g (Table 3). A one-way ANOVA test comparing the hotel and simulation results indicated no statistically significant difference at the 0.01 level. Note that while the model was calibrated to match the empirical average, the close alignment in standard deviation, as well as the similarity in minimum, maximum, and quartile values (25th, 50th, and 75th percentiles), demonstrates the model's ability to reproduce not only central tendencies but also the variability observed in the real-world data. This provides confidence in the model's reliability and supports its use for exploring alternative scenarios. Fig. 6 displays the distribution of both datasets and their respective density functions.

5. Results of large-Scale simulations

5.1. Global sensitivity analysis

We also conducted a sensitivity analysis by varying 14 parameters

Table 2
Parameters obtained from the second optimization.

Parameter	Value
Average indulgence	0.700
Choosing ability	0.600
Food diversity	0.156
Self-control	0.446

Table 3
Descriptive statistics for the hotel data experiment and simulation results.

	Hotel data	Simulation results
Count	493	493
Mean	27.94	30.20
Standard deviation	15.14	14.68
Minimum	0.00	3.44
25 %	16.77	20.00
50 %	26.32	27.60
75 %	36.43	37.36
Maximum	104.27	108.40

related to agents’ motives’ importance, abilities, opportunities; number of guests and guest composition. For motives and abilities, the min-max values in Table 4 refer to the range of population-average importance values assigned to agents in the simulation. All motives and abilities were assigned the same standard deviation for their importance values, with this SD parameter varied between 0.05 and 0.20 across simulations. To facilitate analysis, the average importance of indulgence and conformism was the same among business and non-business agents. We used Latin Hypercube Sampling (LHS) to systematically explore the entire parameter space with 50,000 unique combinations. This decision was informed by Prowse et al. (2016), who recommend such an approach when the number of input parameters is large and the goal is explorative, i.e., to screen the model for important patterns, nonlinearities, and interaction effects. Our study follows this guidance by prioritizing broad coverage of the parameter space and relying on visual consistency in the output to assess stability. Further, in line with Prowse et al.’s (Prowse et al., 2016) approach, we used multi-dimensional visualizations to examine how combinations of parameters shape model outcomes. These plots allowed us to visually identify both main effects, interaction patterns, and nonlinearities.

To understand the effect of each parameter (Table 4) on the amount of leftovers generated, we first examined a correlation matrix. These matrices also included an index representing the amount of food agents served themselves at (a) the first serving, (b) extra servings, and (c) all servings (first + extra servings). To create these indexes, we tracked the

number and type of portion sizes agents served at first and extra servings. The number of portion sizes was first corrected by the number of agents in the simulation and then weighted by the average amount of food according to the portion size. Large, normal, small, and none portion sizes contained, on average, 400, 300, 200, and 0 g of food, respectively. Thus, the weights used to calculate the index were 1, 0.75, 0.5, and 0 for large, normal, small, and none portion sizes, respectively. The index can be calculated using the following equation (7):

$$Index = \left(\frac{S_{portions} * 0.5}{N_{agents}} \right) + \left(\frac{N_{portions} * 0.75}{N_{agents}} \right) + \left(\frac{L_{portions} * 1.0}{N_{agents}} \right), \quad (7)$$

We analyzed the results of the sensitivity analysis regarding the effect they had on the amount of leftovers in grams (g). Leftovers were classified in three different types: (a) those from non-preferred food, (b) those from preferred food, and (c) total leftovers (from preferred/non-preferred food).

Table 4
Parameter space for the global sensitivity analysis. The “Min” and “Max” columns indicate the lower and upper bounds of the parameter ranges explored in the simulations; for motives and abilities, these are the population-average values used as the mean for assigning agent values. CA = choosing ability.

Parameters		Min	Max
Motive Importances	Average Hunger	0.66	1.00
	Average Fullness	0.00	0.33
	Average desire to control weight	0.00	1.00
	Average Indulgence	0.00	1.00
	Average Conformism	0.00	1.00
	Average Sustainability	0.00	1.00
Abilities	Average CA Business	0.00	1.00
	Average CA Non-business	0.00	1.00
	Average CA Self-control	0.00	1.00
	Food Diversity	0.05	0.20
	Small Plate	True/False	
Agent’s composition	Number of agents	50	300
	Proportion of business guests	0.00	1.00

Fig. 6. Distribution of amount of leftovers (grams per guest per day): a) data collected at hotels and b) simulation results. Density distribution of the amount of leftovers (grams per guest per day): c) data collected at hotels and d) simulation results.

Table 5 presents the results of a *t*-test between simulations with normal plate sizes and small plate sizes for the amount of leftovers generated from preferred, non-preferred, and preferred + non-preferred food (n = 25,000 simulations per condition, each involving 100 agents; assumptions of normality and homogeneity of variance were visually inspected and deemed acceptable). In simulations with normal plates, the amount of leftovers is higher in leftovers from preferred food, when it comes to leftovers from non-preferred food no significant differences are observed.

To avoid confounded results according to the limitations presented by the availability of normal or small plate sizes, the following analyses are divided into simulations with small plate or normal plate size.

5.1.1. Factors correlated with the amount of leftovers in simulations using normal and small plate sizes

Table 6 presents the factors that had a correlation coefficient >0.05 and p-value <0.05 with the number of leftovers from preferred food (for correlations with non-preferred food, total amount of food, and the full correlation matrices, see Supplementary Material). In simulations with normal plate size, the amount of leftovers was positive correlated with the amount of food served initially, during extra servings, and all servings, with extra servings having the highest effect. In other words, the more food agents served themselves, the higher the amount of leftovers, particularly during extra servings. Similarly, in simulations with small plate sizes, the amount of leftovers was also correlated with the initial amount of food served and overall amount of food served. However, no significant correlation was found with the amount of food served during extra servings (Table 6).

In simulations with both normal and small plate sizes, the amount of leftovers from preferred food was negatively correlated with conformism and sustainability motives. Hence, the amount of leftovers was lesser the higher the importance of conformism and sustainability (for correlations with non-preferred food, total amount of food, and the full correlation matrices, see supplementary material).

To better explore the data, we created a six-dimensional figure illustrating the amount of leftovers generated from preferred food and their correlations with variables previously identified. Fig. 7 shows the number of leftovers (y-axis) plotted against the amount of food served during extra servings (x-axis). The point color indicates the amount of food served initially, while the x-facet and y-facet represent conformism and sustainability values, respectively, each binned into 0.1 ranges. This analysis is based on simulations with a normal plate size; a similar figure for simulations with a small plate size, which shows qualitatively similar results, is included in the supplementary material.

From Fig. 7, we observe that both conformism and sustainability have the most significant impact on the number of leftovers. Other parameters also affect the number of leftovers, but their influence depends on whether the values of sustainability and conformism fall within the ranges of [0,0.3] and [0,0.4], respectively (as shown in the top-left graphs of Fig. 7). At higher values of sustainability and conformism, the number of leftovers is reduced to zero.

6. Discussion

Here we have outlined an agent-based model of eating behaviors related to FLW at a hotel breakfast buffet. The model provides new insights into our understanding of how certain social norms, motives,

Table 5 Average leftovers per agent per day (in grams) in simulations with normal or small plate size.

Leftovers from:	Normal plate	Small plate	t-test p-value
preferred food	4.82	4.41	<0.001
non-preferred food	11.2	11.3	0.232
preferred + non-preferred food	16.0	15.7	0.081

Table 6 Correlates of number of leftovers in simulations with normal and small Plates. NS = not significant.

Correlation type	Normal Plate		Small Plate	
	Factor	Coeff.	Factor	Coeff.
Positive	Amount of food at		Amount of food at	
	Initial servings	0.16	Initial servings	0.16
	Extra servings	0.30	Extra servings	NS
Negative	All servings	0.29	All servings	0.12
	Conformism	-0.39	Conformism	-0.40
	Sustainability	-0.38	Sustainability	-0.38

abilities and opportunities influence such behaviors. By establishing a theoretical foundation that unifies the MOA and HUMAT frameworks, we have also advanced efforts in the field of complex systems and social simulation to incorporate more realistic psychological architectures in order to enhance policy-oriented modeling of issues related to sustainable and responsible consumption.

Results from the sensitivity analysis revealed that the model is sensitive to all motives and self-control, generating significantly different results for different inputs. It is worth noting that the model is extremely sensitive to initial conditions regarding conformism and sustainability. Slight variations in these two motives can drastically affect the model's output. Interestingly, they are correlated with the amount of food served, and the amount of food served is indeed correlated with several motives. Prior studies show that, in a hospitality context, the guest's perception of sustainability value has a significant effect on food waste reduction behavior (Alsuwaidi et al., 2022).

Another ABM study showed that plate waste food was reduced by 30 % by reducing plate size to small (Ravandi and Jovanovic, 2019), and other experimental studies have reported similar findings (Hansen et al., 2015) (Kallbekken and Sælen, 2013). In contrast, in our ABM we observed a more modest reduction, 8.51 % less food waste with small plates, particularly for preferred food. This discrepancy likely stems from the fact that our ABM isolates the effect of plate size while explicitly controlling for a range of psychological and contextual factors, including hunger, sustainability concerns, social norms, and individual abilities. For example, empirical studies may combine multiple interventions, such as smaller plates with social cues like messages encouraging additional buffet visits (Kallbekken and Sælen, 2013), making it difficult to disentangle the specific contribution of plate size. Moreover, our results represent averaged outcomes across a wide range of parameter settings, whereas the specific conditions and values underlying empirical studies are often unknown. As our model suggests, variations in factors such as cultural values (e.g., sustainability, conformism) can significantly influence food waste behaviors, particularly the amount of leftovers. Therefore, while our findings qualitatively align with previous literature, they suggest that the effectiveness of plate size interventions may be highly context-dependent. Importantly, the ability to calibrate our model to empirical data highlights its flexibility and potential applicability across diverse real-world settings. This reinforces the value of agent-based modeling for uncovering underlying mechanisms and informing more nuanced, targeted interventions.

Compared to existing ABMs such as Ravandi et al. (Ravandi and Jovanovic, 2019), our model introduces several key innovations that enhance both realism and applicability. While Ravandi's model explores the impact of plate size on food waste and guest satisfaction, it relies primarily on theoretical assumptions about hunger and appetite and lacks empirical calibration. In contrast, our model integrates the HUMAT socio-cognitive architecture with the MOA framework, allowing agents to make decisions based on a set of motives, opportunities, and abilities. It also incorporates internal feedback mechanisms such as cognitive dissonance and social influence, resulting in a richer and more psychologically grounded behavioral structure. Moreover, our model explicitly includes social norms and differentiates agents by guest type

Fig. 7. Amount of leftovers from preferred food and its relation to other parameters and amount of food at initial and extra servings.

(e.g., gender, business vs. non-business travelers). Finally, the model is empirically validated using real-world hotel data, thereby increasing confidence in its explanatory and predictive power. These features collectively position our model as a more robust and versatile tool for testing targeted, context-specific interventions to reduce food waste in buffet settings.

6.1. Limitations and future work

Our model, like any other, has its fair share of limitations. First, the experimental data used for calibration was collected exclusively from Nordic hotels and reflect only average plate waste per guest. As such, the dataset may reflect region-specific behavioral patterns. The dataset does not provide individual-level granularity (e.g., by gender, age, or guest type) and is affected by seasonal variations, limiting our ability to represent behavioral heterogeneity or validate to subgroup- or individual-level patterns.

Second, while the model replicates the average and variability of food waste observed in the empirical data, we have not yet conducted a formal predictive validity assessment using out-of-sample or independent datasets. As such, the model’s generalizability beyond the calibration context remains untested.

Third, the model was calibrated using “control group” data (i.e., in the absence of any intervention messaging). Intervention mechanisms were deliberately excluded at this stage to avoid confounding the baseline decision architecture. Our objective in this phase is to test the internal plausibility and behavioral realism of the core mechanisms. This provides a necessary foundation for future simulations that will incorporate messaging-based interventions using experimental data.

Fourth our current implementation does not capture behavioral variation across cultural or demographic groups, such as collectivist

versus individualist orientations or business versus leisure travelers. Although we include guest-type categories and gender in the model, we did not implement explicit differences in the current simulations in order to simplify the model and gain an initial understanding of emerging behavioral patterns.

Fifth, a structural limitation involves how sustainability is modeled. Currently, sustainability motives influence only the decision to finish the food, not portion selection. This operationalization was based on empirical evidence indicating stronger associations between sustainability and food waste reduction than with portioning behavior ((Zhu and Liu, 2024; Visschers et al., 2016; Abrahamse and Steg, 2013); see also CHORIZO Deliverable 3.4 (CHORIZO Project Consortium, 2024b) for a review of related literature). This implementation also reflects how sustainability norms often manifest through post-hoc social or moral expectations, such as being told to finish one’s food due to waste-related guilt or familial pressure, which are more commonly tied to meal completion than to portioning behavior. We therefore restricted the sustainability motive to the finishing stage, with plans to extend its influence to portion selection in the next model version (see below).

Sixth, we acknowledge that the complexity of the model introduces a potential “black-box” risk, where the transmission pathways between rules, parameters, and outcomes may be difficult to interpret. While exhaustively tracing all rule-level interactions is impractical, we mitigate this through a comprehensive global sensitivity analysis and the use of empirically grounded mechanisms based on the HUMAT and MOA frameworks. These frameworks ensure behavioral plausibility and internal consistency.

Many of the limitations described above will be addressed in upcoming analyses through the exploration of new scenarios. In particular, we plan to.

1. Simulate alternative guest compositions (e.g., varying proportions of business vs. non-business guests) and culturally diverse populations (e.g., collectivist vs. individualist orientations) to assess the model's applicability across different contexts.
2. Incorporate the impact of positive and provocative messages displayed in the serving area as external interventions. These messages may activate sustainability-related motives (Chen and Jai, 2018) earlier in the decision process, allowing us to examine their influence on portion selection and compare results to the available experimental intervention data.
3. Explore combinations of interventions—such as pairing plate size changes with messaging to assess their joint effectiveness. This will include segmented scenarios reflecting differences in cultural norms, time constraints, and responsiveness to multiple interventions.

These efforts will allow the model to offer more targeted and actionable guidance for diverse buffet settings and enhance its generalizability across real-world applications.

7. Conclusion

In general, our model has been finely tuned to explore the connection between social norms and behavior in relation to food waste in 'all-you-can-eat' buffet settings. Our main aim was to demonstrate how macro-level patterns of food waste can plausibly emerge from the interaction of heterogeneous agents governed by theoretically grounded decision rules (Epstein, 2008). The model formalizes and integrates three complementary theoretical perspectives, HUMAT, MOA, and social norms, into a unified agent-based framework.

Through empirical calibration and systematic sensitivity analysis, this work establishes a baseline level of validity for the model and builds confidence in its ability to reproduce observed FW patterns. By demonstrating the feasibility and plausibility of these mechanisms, we provide a strong explanatory foundation for the model, showing that it can generate behavior that is consistent with real-world tendencies while offering insights into the interplay between individual, contextual, and social drivers.

As such, the model provides a solid foundation for future studies aimed at testing the effectiveness of targeted interventions under different contextual and behavioral scenarios. Thanks to its modular structure and behavioral richness, the model can be readily adapted and calibrated to various contexts such as restaurants, cafeterias, or institutional settings, providing a valuable tool for researchers, policy-makers, and practitioners seeking to understand FW behaviors and promote sustainable and responsible consumption in such contexts. In future work, we will implement and test intervention scenarios such as normative messaging and structural changes, in collaboration with stakeholders and using empirical data from the CHORIZO field experiments, to assess the potential impact of specific interventions.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Ivan Puga-Gonzalez: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Software, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Larissa L. Lima:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Software, Methodology, Formal analysis, Data curation. **Patrycja Antosz:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Project administration, Methodology, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization. **Ernesto Carrella:** Methodology, Data curation. **Elisa Iori:** Writing – review & editing, Conceptualization. **Caterina Rettore:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Methodology, Investigation, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Markus G. Rousseau:** Writing – review & editing, Conceptualization. **F. LeRon Shults:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Conceptualization. **Matteo Vittuari:** Writing – review & editing, Project

administration, Funding acquisition.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.clrc.2025.100333>.

Data availability

I have shared the link to my data/code in the manuscript

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